

A method for screening rice cultivars for cold tolerance at early seedling stage

J. Dome, rice breeder, BP 29 Adrao-West African Rice Development Association, Richard Toll, Senegal; G. Pateña, research assistant, and B. S. Vergara, plant physiologist, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

In temperate areas, high-elevation areas, or some newly-cultivated tropic areas, low temperatures may kill, retard, or weaken the growth of pregerminated seeds.

This method is proposed to test cold tolerance of rice cultivars at the early seedling stage.

For each rice to be screened, put 20 germinated seeds in each of 3 vials or small bottles lined with moistened tissue paper. When seedlings have a coleoptile of 5 mm, subject to 4°C cold treatment for 10 days. Allow the seedlings to recover for 10 days at ambient temperature in a greenhouse. Then, score for cold tolerance at early seedling stage (see

Score	Vigor	Criteria
		Density
1	Seedling height more than 10 cm, green leaves.	All seedlings alive.
3	Seedling height generally 8-10 cm,	Less than 30% seedlings dead.
5	Seedling height generally 5-7 cm,	30-50% seedlings dead.
7	Seedling height generally 3-4 cm,	More than 50% seedlings dead.
9	All seedlings dead, seedling height < 1 cm.	All seedlings dead.

chart).

The reactions of germinated seeds to cold treatment vary considerably with stage of development. Discrimination between cold-tolerant and susceptible cultivars is more obvious if seeds subjected to cold treatment have a well-developed coleoptile of about 5 mm and traces of chlorophyll. Less-developed seedling of a susceptible rice could show little effect of the cold treatment and be mistaken for a tolerant cultivar.

Rices also differ in developmental habits. Generally, most indicas reach the optimum stage of development after 72 hours of incubation. Japonica varieties take longer. It is advisable to divide a

collection according to the rates of development of the types and subject seedlings to cold treatment only when they have arrived at the correct stage.

To prevent drying of the seedlings, check moisture content of the vials regularly. Include a fungicide in first watering to avoid fungus damage.

Score samples for both seedling vigor and density of surviving plants and take the mean of the two scores.

With this method, Barkat (K78-13), Baekgogna, and Jo Do were found tolerant (score 1 to 3) at the early seedling stage; Taichung Sen Yu 229, Dumai, Suweon 287, and IR8 were sensitive (5 to 9). ■

Rice pollination characteristics related to high temperature tolerance

D. J. Mackill, research fellow, International Rice Research Institute

High temperature-induced sterility has not been an important problem in traditional cropping patterns. However, with the development of irrigation systems for dry season cropping of rice and the

expansion of rice production in semiarid countries, high temperature tolerance may become an important breeding objective. Several rice cultivars and breeding lines differing in reaction to high temperature at the anthesis stage were studied for their ability to shed pollen on the stigma.

Spikelets of each variety or line were collected in the afternoon of the day of anthesis. The number of pollen grains

on the stigma was counted and stigmas with more than 100 pollen grains were scored as 100. Plants from the 29°/21° and 38°/27°C glasshouse rooms of the IRRI phytotron and from the field at IRRI were sampled in the 1980 dry season and the 1981 wet season. Percentage of fertility or filled grains was measured on plants grown in the phytotron. The number of pollen grains per anther was measured on plants growing in the field.

Percent fertility, pollen grains per stigma, and pollen grains per anther for 6 rices grown in the phytotron and in the field at IRRI, 1980 wet season and 1981 dry season.

Variety or line	Phytotron				Field		
	Fertility (%)		Pollen grains (no./stigma)		Pollen grains (no./stigma)		Pollen grains (no./anther),
	29°/21°C ^a	38°/21°C	29°/21°C	38°/27°C	1980 WS	1981%	1981 DS
<i>Heat tolerant</i>							
N22	88.9 bc	30.0 ab	65.4 b	65.6 a	<i>b</i>	85.7 a	1085 b
IR2006-P12-12-2-2	97.9 a	31.8 a	84.9 a	68.2 a	86.8 a	80.8 a	1908 a
IET4658 (UPR96-1-1-1)	88.1 bc	19.5 bc	66.3 b	63.0 a	76.8 a	72.9 a	1255 b
<i>Heat susceptible</i>							
IR28	71.4 d	3.6 d	33.1 c	12.5 b	60.9 b	70.7 a	1800 a
IR1561-228-3-3	94.8 ab	4.3 d	32.6 c	19.6 b	54.0 bc	40.8 b	1705 a
IR52	84.1 cd	3.1 d	17.3 c	1.8 b	42.4 c	38.2 b	1750 a

^aWithin a column means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bNo measurement was made for N22 in the wet season of 1980.

In the phytotron fertility was greatly reduced in plants at 38° / 27° C during flowering. Three heat-tolerant rices had higher fertility at 38° / 27° C. This was apparently not related to the fertility at 29° / 21° C, because the heat-susceptible line IR1561-228-3-3 had high fertility at this temperature. Heat-tolerant rices had more pollen grains per stigma than susceptible rices at both temperatures. In tolerant rices, high temperature had little

effect on the number of pollen grains per stigma. In susceptible rices, high temperature greatly reduced the number of pollen grains per stigma (see table).

Pollen shedding on the stigma in field-grown plants showed the same trend as in phytotron-grown plants. The amount of pollen shed on the stigma was not related to the number of pollen grains per anther; two tolerant rices, N22 and IET4658, had significantly less

pollen grains per anther than the other lines.

It appears that the amount of pollen shed on the stigma is related to the time of anther dehiscence in relation to filament elongation. This trait, which distinguishes heat-tolerant from heat-susceptible rices, is expressed under field conditions even in the absence of high temperature. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Rice bacterial blight status in the Punjab, India

G. L. Raina, pathologist; G. S. Sidhu, senior breeder; and P. K. Saini, research associate, Punjab Agricultural University, Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India

Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* has been known to occur in Punjab State of India since the 1940s. The disease, first observed in Gurdaspur district, was called *purarh* or *pansukh* in the local language, which means blighting or leaf-drying. It was considered to be due to some physiological disorder, and only in 1965 was its etiology established.

BB has been found to appear every year in varying degrees in different areas. During 1980 kharif (dry season), BB assumed an epiphytotic form and caused considerable yield loss throughout the state, in some areas as high as 60-70%. The kresak phase of the disease was also recorded in some fields for the first time.

Increase in BB incidence and severity may be attributed to higher nitrogen applications, very early transplanting, and conducive macro- and microclimatic conditions. The possibility of pathogenic variability also exists.

In the Punjab, the rice season lasts from May to October. Because almost all rice straw is burnt in the fields, there does not seem to be any chance for the bacterium to be carried over to the next crop season through infected rice straw. The possibility of pathogen survival in

Incidence of bacterial blight in Punjab, India.

Year	BB incidence
1975	Moderate to severe
1976	Low to severe
1977	Low to severe
1978	Low to severe
1979	Moderate to severe
1980	Severe

the stubble of infected plants is not ruled out, although harvested rice fields are immediately replanted to wheat.

The speculation is that BB bacterium carries over to the next crop season through infected seed. It is also possible that the pathogen survives in the rhizosphere of wheat and other nonhost plants during winter. Studies are being initiated to identify the source of carry-over. Studies on variability also are in progress. Some resistant donors have been identified and are being used in the breeding program. Progeny will be screened under artificial inoculation conditions. Attempts are being made to develop differentials and to test bacterial isolates from all over the state.

In vitro inhibition of rice fungal pathogens by extracts from higher plants

V. Damodaram Naidu and V. T. John, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Leaves of *Polyalthea longifolia*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, and *Cymbopogon* sp. were macerated. The aqueous

extracts were mixed at varying concentrations with potato dextrose agar and tested for antifungal activity by poison-food technique. Rhizomes of *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) and *Curcuma longa* (turmeric) were also tested for antifungal activity. Fungal pathogens tested were *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Sclerotium oryzae*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

Extracts from plants inhibited the growth of most fungal pathogens tested. The growth inhibition was greater in *R. solani* and *S. oryzae* than in other pathogens.

Extracts from *Azadirachta indica*, *Catharanthus roseus*, *Calotropis gigantea*, *Allium cepa*, *A. sativum*, *Eichhornia crassipes*, and *Clerodendron sp.* showed poor growth inhibition of the fungal pathogens tested. ■

Nilaparvata bakeri transmission of rice ragged stunt virus

T. Morinaka, Tropical Agriculture Research Center, Yatabe, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305, Japan; D. Chettanachit, M. Putta, A. Parejarearn, and S. Disthaporn. Division of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok 9, Thailand

Rice ragged stunt virus transmission abilities of *Nephotettix virescens*, *Recilia dorsalis*, *Sogatella furcifera*, and *Nilaparvata bakeri* were tested. Nymphs of *N. virescens* and adults of *R. dorsalis*